

Who, How and Where of Occupational Corneal Foreign Body: A Prospective, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice Study in a Hospital Based Setting in North Karnataka

Venkatram Katti¹, Vivekanand Jivangi², Satish D Shet³, Srividya Balakrishnan⁴,
Aishwarya H N⁵, Prerana M R⁶

^{1,2,3} Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Hubli, Karnataka, India

^{4,5,6} Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Karnataka, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Srividya Balakrishnan

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Abstract:

Purpose: Occupational exposure is one of the most common causes for corneal foreign body in India. Our study provides information regarding different occupations and settings that contribute to superficial corneal foreign body in the patients visiting Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Hubli OPD. This study also analyzes the risk factors, outcomes, demographic characteristics and attitude of workers with superficial corneal foreign body injury.

Aim: Our study aims to identify the basic knowledge, attitude, beliefs and behaviours of workers towards occupational corneal foreign body injury.

Methods: This is a prospective hospital-based study done on 60 patients who presented with superficial corneal foreign body to the OPD at Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Hubli. The patients were asked to answer a questionnaire to assess their knowledge, attitude and practice pertaining to occupational corneal foreign body and were examined to determine the nature of the injury. Apart from this, all patients also underwent a comprehensive eye examination and appropriate methods were undertaken to remove the corneal foreign body under aseptic precautions.

Results: 95% of the patients were male with a mean age of 35.07 years. The metal industry (welding) was responsible for 58.3% of presentations, with 43.3% of them having completed middle school education. 93.3% of patients had not used any protective eye wears and 36.7% attempted self removal of the foreign body. Only 35% had knowledge on harm to the eye caused by self removal of foreign body, and only 45% of the patients had receive health education at their workplace on prevention and complications of occupational corneal foreign body.

Conclusion: Occupational corneal foreign has become a common preventable ocular morbidity and this can be easily prevented by proper usage of protective measures. Health education plays a vital role in creating awareness about the importance of using protective eye wears and possible complications of corneal foreign body among the workers irrespective of their level of education.

Keywords: Occupational corneal foreign body (CFB), Self-Removal, Protective Eye Wears, Health Education.

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Introduction

Occupational eye injuries have become a common source of ocular morbidity, especially among industrial workers and construction workers. [1] However, most of these are superficial corneal injuries by the fall of foreign body into the eye. A superficial corneal foreign body is a common presentation to the emergency department occurring frequently in the setting of construction and machining. [5] In spite of them being superficial injuries to the cornea, they can cause decrease in the quality of vision by forming scars in the visual axis, secondary infections like keratitis, endophthalmitis etc. [2]

Patients most commonly present with symptoms like foreign body sensation, pain, redness, watering of the eyes and blurred vision. History of the inciting event is almost always present. [8] Thus this corneal injury is characteristically painful and the patient may be put to a good deal of inconvenience and lose time from work. [7] Thus, we can say that ocular injuries due to occupational reasons bear a significant economic burden. [3]

It has been observed that welders are at particularly high risk for eye injuries (31.9%). [9] The most common source of welding-related injuries is cold

particles, most often metal. The welding process may expose workers to various sources of mechanical, radiant, thermal or chemical energy. Therefore, industries should stress the importance of wearing eye protection constantly while working with metal pieces. [10] However, it is not appropriate to solely attribute the workplace injury to external factors. It should be emphasized that human factors also play an important role in the occurrence of these work-related injuries. Therefore, appropriate planning to increase the level of knowledge, attitude and safe behavioural practices can decrease the workplace accidents and improve workers' health in different aspects. [10, 11] Apart from welders, even those who work in construction industry, automobile repairs, wood cutters, agriculture workers, tailors also face such injuries. Also it has been observed that people from all these occupations, come with recurrent FBs in their eyes, depicting the need for good health education on 'safety from occupational hazards' and also need to be provided with good quality safety equipment to prevent such hazards.

Superficial corneal FB is very much a preventable occupational hazard, and the investment in their prevention is easily justified. Providing its workers with safety goggles, head shields, and other personal protective equipment and educating its workers on the need for and how to use this safety equipment can prevent 90% of such injuries. Improving workplace standards and providing appropriate training for supervisors can contribute further to preventing these occupational hazards. [2, 3]

The purpose of the current study is to determine the occupation, mechanism of injury, level of education, use of safety equipment at the time of accident, health education on 'safety from occupational hazards', and other demographics of the patients presenting to the OPD of Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Hubli, with superficial corneal foreign body acquired during their occupation.

Methods

The study adhered to the basic tenets of Declaration of Helsinki. Institutional ethical committee clearance was obtained before the start of the study. This is a hospital based prospective study which was done at Karnataka Medical College and Research Institute, Hubli. All patients who presented with a superficial corneal foreign body sustained during occupational work during a period of 6 months (March 2024 to August 2024) were included in this study. All patients were asked a set of questions by the ophthalmologist in their vernacular language and the responses were recorded. Written consent was taken from all the patients in their vernacular language before including them in the study.

All patients were examined under the slit-lamp. The foreign body and rust rings were removed using a sterile 26-gauge needle under topical anaesthesia under aseptic precautions. A topical antibiotic (Ofloxacin eyedrops, four times a day for 1 week) was prescribed after the foreign body was removed. The locations of the FB, rust marks, super-added infection and any corneal scars from previous FBs were noted.

We recorded demographic information of each patient, which included age, gender and education. We enquired about their occupation and activity at the time of incident. Later the patients were asked to answer a set of questions to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of the patient regarding eye injury at work. The first two questions were pertaining to the knowledge; the next two questions were asked to know about the attitude of the patients and the last three questions were designed to assess the undertaken practice pertaining to this subject. Their responses were scored as 0 or 1, 0 being undesired and 1 being the desired response. One of the questions was scored as 0, 1 and 2, with 0 being the undesired answer and 2 being the most desired answer. The summary of the questionnaire is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Score allotment to the KAP questionnaire

KAP Questionnaire assessment	Response	Score
Does the patient have knowledge about the detrimental effect of repeated corneal foreign body exposure to the vision	No	0
	Yes	1
Does the patient have knowledge about the harm that self removal of foreign body can cause	No	0
	Yes	1
Is the patient willing to follow appropriate safety measures at his/her workplace	No	0
	Yes	1
Is the patient willing to encourage his friends and colleagues to also adopt appropriate safety measures at his/her workplace	No	0
	Yes	1
What was the time gap btw injury and first visit to the ophthalmologist	> 72 hr	0
	24-72 hr	1
	<24 hr	2
Was the patient using protective glass/ helmet during the incident	No	0
	Yes	1
Has the patient attempted to self remove the foreign body	Yes	0
	No	1

Figure 1: Two images showing the superficial corneal foreign body which came to KMC-RI, Hubli OPD

Results

We examined 60 patients with corneal foreign body acquired due to occupational work. 95% (n=57) of patients were male and 5% (n=3) were female (Table 2). Most of the affected patients (45%, n=27) belonged to the age group of 15-29 years, followed by 30-44 years (30%, n=18) (Fig 3). In our study, metal work industry (welding) was responsible for 58.3% (n=35) of presentations, construction work industry for 20% (n=12) while automobile repair sector 10% (n=6), agriculture sector 6.7% (n=4), and tailors were 5% (n=3) (Fig 2). 53.3% (n=32) of the patients were found to visit the ophthalmologist within a time period of 24-72 hours, followed by 40% (n=24) visiting within 24 hours and the remaining 6.7% (n=4) visiting after 72 hours (Table 6). Most of the patients had completed middle school (Table 3). 51.7% (n=31) had history of previous corneal foreign bodies while the remaining had no previous history of corneal foreign bodies (Table 5). 56.7% (n=34) had knowledge that repetitive corneal foreign body can cause visual morbidity by scar formation or can lead to worse

complications like keratitis or endophthalmitis (Table 6).

Under slit lamp examination 55% (n=33) had superficial corneal foreign body in the peripheral cornea, 40% (n=24) had in paracentral cornea while only 5% (n=3) of the patients had involvement of central cornea (Table 4). Out of 60 patients 36.7% (n=22) of them gave history of attempt to self removal of corneal foreign body with various unsterile methods and 35% (n=21) of the patients had knowledge that self removal of foreign body can cause complications like corneal ulcers/ endophthalmitis and further cause vision decline (Table 6).

When enquired whether a protective gear was used or not, 93.3% (n=56) of the patients did not use any protective glass/helmet (Table 6). 61.7% (n=37) said that they would follow safety measures that was advised to them from next time and that they would also encourage their friends and co-workers to follow the same.

Table 2: Showing the gender distribution

Gender	n	Percent
Female	3	5
Male	57	95

Figure 2: Showing the occupation of the patients

Figure 3: Pie chart showing the distribution of age of the patients

Table 3: Showing the level of education

Level of education	n	%	mean	SD	Test
completed high school	19	31.7	3.79	1.84	ANOVA test P=0.025
completed middle school	26	43.3	3.54	1.65	
completed primary school	7	11.7	5.29	2.36	
less than primary school	8	13.3	5.25	0.89	

Table 4: Showing the location of superficial corneal foreign body

FB Location	n	%	mean	SD	Test
central cornea	3	5	3.33	2.52	ANOVA test P=0.268
paracentral cornea	24	40	3.67	1.93	
peripheral cornea	33	55	4.39	1.69	

Table 5: Showing the history of similar incident and health education

		n	%	mean	SD	Test
Similar Incident	YES	31	51.7	3.77	2	T test P=0.232
	NO	29	48.3	4.34	1.63	
Health education	YES	27	45	4.85	1.63	T test P=0.002
	NO	33	55	3.39	1.75	

Table 6: Showing the response to the KAP questionnaire

KAP Questionnaire		n	Percent
Does the patient have knowledge about the detrimental effect of repeated corneal foreign body exposure to the vision	No	34	56.7
	Yes	26	43.3
Does the patient have knowledge about the harm that self-removal of foreign body can cause	No	39	65
	Yes	21	35
Is the patient willing to follow appropriate safety measures at his/her workplace	No	23	38.3
	Yes	37	61.7
Is the patient willing to encourage his friends and colleagues to also adopt appropriate safety measures at his/her workplace	No	23	38.3
	Yes	37	61.7
What was the time gap btw injury and first visit to the ophthalmologist	> 72 hr	4	6.7
	24-72 hr	32	53.3
	<24 hr	24	40
Was the patient using protective glass/ helmet during the incident	No	56	93.3
	Yes	4	6.7
Has the patient attempted to self remove the foreign body	Yes	22	36.7
	No	38	63.3

Discussion

Superficial corneal foreign body falls under the category of minor ocular trauma. If treated on time many complications can be prevented but if delayed or neglected can lead to reduced visual acuity because of complications like keratitis, corneal opacity and endophthalmitis.

In our study, 95% of the affected patients were male. Similar findings were found in a study conducted by Shrestha et al. [8] Males, being the active income generators of the family are more likely to seek jobs in metal industries than females which explains the male predominance in the study.

Most of the affected patients (45%, n=27) belonged to the age group of 15-29 years. Similar findings were found in the study performed by Zeynep Ozkurt et al [6] and Agarwal et al. [4] This age group should thus be the target population to receive more strict and repetitive health education regarding 'safety from occupational hazards'. [12]

We found that 58.3% of the patients worked in metal industry most of them involved in welding work. This is supported by the study conducted by Lombardi, Pannala, Sorock et al where welding (31.9%) and grinding (22.5%) were the most common activities at the time of injury. Activities also included cleaning or brushing (3.7%) or observing or being a bystander (3.0%) among others. Almost 22% of activities were non-classifiable due to a lack of information. Injury sources were frequently particulates or small solids (63.4%) and ultraviolet rays (19.7%). [9]

Most of the patients in our study 43.3% had completed their education till middle school with a significant correlation between level of education and the 'Knowledge' parameter of this study ($p = 0.025$). In a similar study done by H Sanaei Nasab et al, there was a significant relation between level of knowledge and level of education ($p < 0.001$). But,

in spite of a significant relationship between knowledge and educational level of the workers, no statistically significant relation was reported between knowledge with attitude and practice of safe behaviours. This result indicated that level of education or knowledge alone, will not lead to positive attitudes or practice of safe behaviours. That is to promote safety culture, we need to design specific educational programs which consider the characteristics of workers and their workplace conditions. [11] We need to target the right group of people at risk and provide them detailed and repetitive health education on this subject. [14-16]

We examined the patient's knowledge about repetitive corneal foreign body injury and 43.3% of patients were aware about the possible complications like keratitis, corneal opacities, endophthalmitis etc. We asked the patients whether they were aware about the harm of attempt to remove the foreign body on their own and 65% had no knowledge on harm that self removal can cause to the person's vision. This was supported by a study conducted by Shrestha T et al, in which 21.67% of the cases attempted self removal [8] and In a study conducted by Zeynep Ozkurt et al, 52% of the patients had attempted to remove the corneal foreign body by themselves.[6]

The most common location of the corneal foreign body in our study was peripheral i.e. 55%, followed by paracentral i.e. 40% and then central i.e. 5%. Our findings were similar to the findings seen in the study conducted by Shrestha et al in which they found that most common location was peripheral i.e. 38.33%, followed by paracentral i.e. 31.66%, and then central i.e. 30%. [8]

In our study, 53.3% of the patients visited the ophthalmologist within 24-72 hours of the incident, which is consistent with the study conducted by Ozkurt ZG et al where the mean duration between the injury and the first visit to an ophthalmologist

was 2.16 days and ranged between 0 and 21 days[6] and in another study by Shrestha et al 80% of the patients were found to visit within 3 days of the incident. [8]

It was found in our study that only 6.7% of the patients had used a protective glass or helmet while working and were wearing it at the time of injury. In a similar study conducted by Agarwal et al demonstrated that only 53% of patients were provided with protective glasses and conversely, 47% had not been provided with protective glasses. Of these, only 27% of patients with protective glasses were wearing it at the time of injury. Of the reasons for not wearing the eye protection, 6% had simply forgotten to wear the glasses and 12% believed the eye protection to be too uncomfortable [Table 4]. This suggests that eye protection is not adequately enforced in the workplace and ergonomics is a potential inhibitive factor for employees. [4]

Health education on the risk of eye injury is part of certain occupations. [4] Our study demonstrated that only 45% of the patients had received education on occupational hazards and 55% did not receive any health education regarding occupational hazards. In our study, a significant relation was found between health education and occupational corneal foreign body (t test, $p=0.002$). This result indicates that health education plays a significant role in preventing the occupational corneal foreign body. According to a study conducted by Agarwal et al, 49% of patients that presented had received education on occupational hazards, and conversely, 51% of the patients did not receive health education on such hazards. This awareness and education were considerably lower in the construction and metallic industry workers, which in turn were two of the most affected business sectors. [17] In contrast, a study in Southwest China [12] demonstrated that among a patient base of 453 patients, 22.5% received safety training. Despite the low health education, it was found that 67% of patients that presented were aware that their occupation entailed the risk of injuries related to the eye.[18] However, a smaller percentage of 58% were aware that eye related injuries could incur significant visual impairment. This suggests that employees are generally aware of risk of eye injury, but do not appreciate the serious nature of such injuries. It will be a good, rational step to arrange regular, repetitive educational meetings with workers regarding work-related ocular injuries, possible consequences of such injuries, and measures that should be taken in case of occupational injuries. [10] Better education and training of the workforce is required to prevent ergo-ophthalmologic injuries. [5]

Conclusion

Corneal foreign body occurs across a number of occupations in the construction industry, not just metallic workers. Among a population that is generally poorly educated and have nominal understanding of the impact that corneal foreign body can have on vision, health education is necessary to address this problem. Thus, it may be advisable for all business sectors, especially the more affected metallic and construction industries, along with eye care organizations, to establish regular and comprehensive educative workshops or awareness programs to prevent such disastrous incidents to their employees in the near future. The incidence and hence the prevalence of occupational corneal foreign bodies and their associated complications can be reduced by creating awareness amongst the people and encouraging them to use protective eye wears.

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